

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' RESEARCH SKILLS THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Abstract. *This study explored the development of students' research skills through the use of interactive methods. The author examines the theoretical and methodological foundations of pedagogical technology in this context. This study proposes a model based on a mini-research cycle and substantiates the didactic potential of the SPARK interactive method.*

Keywords: *interactive methods, research skills, pedagogical technology, mini-research cycle, SPARK method, scientific inquiry.*

Introduction. In the modern higher education system, developing students' ability to conduct independent scientific inquiry, analyze problem situations, and draw evidence-based conclusions is considered a key pedagogical task. Today, rather than transmitting ready-made knowledge, priority is given to engaging students in active scientific activities based on their personal experiences. Such an approach contributes to the effective organization of students' research activities, enhances their professional readiness and intellectual development, and increases their competitiveness in the labor market.

Therefore, scientific analyses of teaching methods aimed at developing research skills are of particular relevance. Pedagogical studies indicate that interactive teaching methods significantly enhance students' capacity for independent scientific inquiry, fostering scientific thinking, analytical abilities and reflective skills. These processes provide a solid foundation for students' successful, professional development.

Literature review. A.R. Khodjaboyev, I.A. Khusanov and U.N. Nishonaliyev interprets teaching methods as a methodological tool that connects the objectives, content, and outcomes of vocational education. They emphasized that active and problem-based methods contribute to the development of students' independent thinking and their capacity for scientific inquiry [10].

Saidahmedov highlights that, within the framework of modern pedagogical technologies, students should be formed as active, independent, and inquiry-oriented subjects of the educational process, which constitutes a methodological foundation for the development of research skills [6].

B.T. Jurayev considers the methodology of teaching pedagogical disciplines as an integrated didactic system based on the collaborative activities of teachers and students. According to the author, teaching methods are not merely a means of knowledge transmission but also a key pedagogical factor in activating students' cognitive activity, fostering independent thinking, and guiding them toward scientific inquiry. In particular, problem-based, heuristic, and active methods contribute to the development of students' abilities in analysis, generalization, and drawing conclusions [4].

The reviewed studies demonstrate the significance of active and problem-based methods in developing students' research abilities. However, the application of these methods as systematic pedagogical technologies based on interactive approaches and the comprehensive evaluation of their effectiveness remain insufficiently explored.

In this context, modern international studies emphasize the importance of research-based and interactive approaches in higher-education. According to Healey and Healey and C. Roberts states that students should not be considered passive recipients of knowledge, but as active participants who construct knowledge through inquiry-oriented learning processes [3]. This perspective highlights the necessity of integrating research activities into the educational process.

Minner, Levy, and Century demonstrated that inquiry-based learning (IBL) environments enhance students' abilities to formulate hypotheses, analyze evidence, and draw scientifically grounded conclusions [5]. These findings confirm the effectiveness of inquiry-based approaches in developing research-related competency.

Furthermore, the Research Skill Development (RSD) framework proposed by Willison and O'Regan provides a structured model for the progressive development of research skills in higher education. This framework emphasizes the importance of systematically organizing research activities to foster students' scientific competencies [7].

Empirical evidence supports the effectiveness of these approaches. Abdi's study showed that students taught using inquiry-based learning methods achieved significantly higher academic results than those in traditional learning environments [1]. This demonstrates the practical effectiveness of integrating research-based and interactive methods into education.

In addition, innovative teaching methods play a crucial role in enhancing students' engagement and practical application of knowledge [4]. Such methods stimulate learners' intrinsic motivation, ensure interdisciplinary integration, and organize the learning process through active participation, thereby enabling students to apply their knowledge in practice as well as theoretically [8].

In modern higher education, research skills encompass the ability to independently formulate problems, propose hypotheses, analyze scientific information, construct arguments, draw conclusions, and engage in reflective thinking [9]. These skills should not be developed through isolated methods but through a systematically designed pedagogical technology based on clearly defined indicators.

The issue of systematically designing pedagogical technology is also of considerable importance at the international level. UNESCO reports have recognized pedagogical technologies as key factors in the modernization of education [2].

Thus, the analyzed scientific approaches form the conceptual and methodological foundation for the development of students' research skills through interactive methods in the classroom.

Methodological framework. According to these approaches, pedagogical technology is a systematic method for designing, implementing, and evaluating the educational process. In the 21st century, this concept has further evolved, and pedagogical technology is increasingly viewed as a scientifically grounded process that ensures effective achievement of educational objectives.

Therefore, pedagogical technology based on interactive methods enables the integration of the educational process with research activities. This technology is implemented through the alignment of contemporary pedagogical approaches to learning. Its methodological foundation is formed by the activity-based approach, research-based learning, competency-based approach, and

principle of constructive alignment. These theoretical foundations ensure the conceptual structure and internal logical coherence of technology.

The activity-based approach conceptualizes the learning process as an active cognitive activity for the student. Within this framework, knowledge is not transmitted in a ready-made form but constructed through students' practical and intellectual engagement. Accordingly, interactive methods serve as key tools for ensuring students' active participation in the learning process and improving their performance. As a result, the educational process shifts from passive reception to active investigation.

Research-based learning represents another essential methodological foundation for this technology. This approach involves organizing the educational process according to the logic of scientific inquiry. In this context, the learning process is structured as a cycle that includes problem identification, hypothesis formulation, data collection and analysis, and conclusion. Within this technological framework, interactive methods function as instruments for implementing a mini research model. This enables the systematic development of the elements of scientific thinking among students.

The competency-based approach evaluates learning outcomes not in terms of the volume of knowledge acquired but in terms of an individual's readiness to perform activities. Therefore, interactive methods are aimed not merely at content acquisition but at developing students' ability to independently analyze problems, construct arguments, and engage in reflective thinking. As research skills manifest primarily in the process of activity, they are considered the central outcome of this pedagogical technology.

The principle of constructive alignment ensures the internal coherence of pedagogical technology. According to this principle, the learning objectives, teaching processes, and assessment criteria must be logically interconnected.

Thus, interactive methods are not simply tools for increasing student engagement, but function as a didactic mechanism that reflects the internal logic of the research process within pedagogical technology. This transformed the learning process into a consistent mini-research cycle, ranging from problem identification to reflection.

Based on the aforementioned methodological foundations, a model was developed for the step-by-step development of research skills through the use of interactive methods (Figure 1). The practical implementation of this model is ensured through a pedagogical mechanism organized around the stages of problem identification, hypothesis formulation, data analysis, presentation of results and reflection.

The initial stage of the model is associated with the creation of a problem situation that stimulates students' need for scientific inquiry and fosters cognitive engagement with the phenomenon under study. At this stage, the teacher organizes the learning process in such a way that a certain contradiction emerges between students' prior knowledge and the newly introduced information. This contradiction provokes questioning and creates a need for further inquiry to explain the problem.

In creating a problem situation, tasks are designed based on real-life examples, statistical data, scientific facts or problem-oriented questions. As a result, students were engaged in identifying the problem independently and formulating it as a scientific question. This process enhances students' cognitive interest and prepares them for future research activities.

Figure 1. A model for the step-by-step development of research skills through the use of interactive methods

The effective implementation of this stage is ensured through the use of various, interactive methods. In particular, problem-based learning, case study methods, and brainstorming facilitate active student participation. In addition, the SPARK interactive method developed by the author was applied at this stage. Through this method, the given situation is analyzed, the underlying scientific problem is identified, the key causes and factors are discussed, and essential research questions guiding further inquiry are formulated. As a result, students develop the ability to understand a problem, express it in the form of a scientific question, and prepare for the subsequent stages of the research process.

Methodological description of the Spark Interactive Method. In the process of developing students' research skills, identifying a problem and formulating a scientific question constitute a crucial methodological stage. To effectively organize this process, the SPARK interactive method was developed by the author (Figure 2).

This method enables the systematic organization of students' cognitive engagement in scientific inquiry, including problem analysis and research question formulation. The name of the method is derived from the English word "spark," meaning "a stimulus" or "a trigger of activity." This reflects the core idea of the method, which is to stimulate students' intrinsic motivation for scientific inquiry.

The acronym SPARK represents the key stages of the method: Situation – Problem – Analysis – Research – Knowledge.

This graphical model illustrates the stages of the SPARK method. It represents the research process as a continuous cycle, ranging from the identification of a problem to the formulation of scientific conclusions.

Figure 2. A graphical model of the SPARK interactive method developed by the author

Purpose of the method. The primary objective of the SPARK method is to develop students' ability to analyze problem situations, identify scientific problems and formulate research questions. This method enhances students' cognitive engagement, enables them to analyze the causes and factors of a problem, and supports the identification of initial research directions necessary for scientific inquiry. As a result, students learn to examine the phenomenon under study from multiple perspectives and formulate the problem in the form of a scientific question.

Implementation procedure. The implementation of the SPARK interactive method involves several sequential steps. In the initial stage, a real-life situation related to the studied phenomenon

or problem is presented. In this process, a problem is created using statistical data, scientific facts, problem-based questions, or real-life examples.

In the next stage, students analyze the situation and attempt to identify the core problem. Subsequently, the causes and contributing factors of the problem are discussed and examined from different perspectives. In the following stage, students formulate research questions and determine key directions for further investigation.

In the final stage, the formulated questions were synthesized and adopted as the foundation for subsequent research activities.

Teacher activity. In the implementation of the SPARK method, the teacher acts as both an organizer and facilitator of the learning process. The teacher creates a problem situation, moderates student discussions, and guides students toward independently identifying the problem. During the discussion, the teacher synthesizes students' ideas, directs them toward scientific analysis, and supports the formulation of well-grounded questions. Rather than providing ready-made answers, teachers encourage students' independent thinking and analytical engagement.

Student activity. In this method, students are active participants in the learning process. They analyzed the presented situation, attempted to identify the problem, and expressed their views during group discussions. Students actively engage in identifying the causes of problems, comparing different perspectives, and formulating scientific questions. Through this process, interactive methods contribute to the development of critical thinking, logical reasoning, and scientific discussion skills among students.

Results. The application of the SPARK interactive method contributes to the development of students' abilities to analyze problem situations, identify scientific problems and formulate research questions. Students gain experience in examining phenomena through an analytical approach, comparing different viewpoints, and generating well-founded scientific questions. In addition, the method enhances students' cognitive interest, engages them in scientific inquiry, and provides methodological preparation for the subsequent stages of research activity. The implementation of the SPARK method demonstrated a noticeable improvement in students' research skills

Conclusion. In conclusion, the use of interactive methods in the educational process facilitates the development of students' research skills. The learning process, structured as a mini-research cycle, promotes students' engagement in scientific inquiry and enhances their analytical, critical thinking, and reflective thinking.

The SPARK interactive method supports the development of students' ability to understand problems, formulate scientific questions, and initiate research activities while also increasing their cognitive engagement. The proposed model and methodology ensure the systematic organization of the educational process and the consistent development of the research skills.

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